

THE INFLUENCE OF HEALTH WORKER PRODUCTIVITY ON IMPROVING HEALTH SERVICES AT SETIABUDI PUBLIC HEALTH CENTER, SOUTH JAKARTA

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of health worker productivity on improving health services at the Setiabudi Community Health Center in South Jakarta. The research method used is descriptive quantitative with a sample of 90 respondents. Primary data were collected through questionnaires and processed using the Method of Successive Interval (MSI) to convert ordinal scale data into interval scales before conducting prerequisite tests and hypothesis testing. Data analysis used multiple linear regression. The results of the F test showed that the variables of motivation, income level, work environment, opportunity for achievement, management, and nutritional status simultaneously had a significant effect on health services (F count 12.053; Sig < 0.001) with a contribution (R²) of 46.6%. Partially, the management variable was the most dominant factor influencing service improvement (t count 5.608; Sig < 0.001). The implications of this study emphasize the importance of strengthening the managerial system and work motivation to optimize the quality of public health services.

Keywords: *Productivity, Health Services, MSI, Community Health Center Management.*

INTRODUCTION

Healthcare is a crucial sector in national development because it plays a direct role in improving the quality of human resources. A good healthcare system will impact public health and socioeconomic productivity. As first-level healthcare facilities, community health centers (Puskesmas) play a strategic role in providing healthcare services to the community through promotive, preventive, curative, and rehabilitative efforts. Increasing patient visits often pose challenges in maintaining the quality of healthcare services, particularly regarding the productivity of healthcare workers. Healthcare worker productivity is the ability of healthcare workers to provide effective, efficient, and high-quality services using available resources. High healthcare worker productivity will improve the quality of healthcare services and patient satisfaction. Based on conditions at the Setiabudi Community Health Center in South Jakarta, the number of patient visits each month is quite high, requiring healthcare workers to work optimally. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the impact of healthcare worker productivity on improving healthcare services at the Setiabudi Community Health Center in South Jakarta.

METHOD

This study used a quantitative approach with a survey method. The study population was all healthcare workers working at the Setiabudi Community Health Center in South Jakarta. The number of samples in this study was 90 respondents selected using the proportional random sampling technique. Data collection was conducted using a questionnaire developed based on health worker productivity indicators. The research instrument used a Likert scale with five levels of assessment.

Data analysis was carried out using the multiple linear regression method with the following stages:

1. Validity test
2. Reliability test
3. Classical assumption test
4. Multiple linear regression analysis
5. Hypothesis testing (t-test and F-test)

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6. Coefficient of determination (R^2)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the study show that the productivity of health workers has a significant influence on improving health services at the Setiabudi Community Health Center, South Jakarta.

Respondent Characteristics

Characteristics	Category	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Man	20	22.2%
	Woman	70	77.8%
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Age	20–30 Years	22	24.4%
	31–40 Years	45	50.0%
	41–50 Years	18	20.0%
	>50 Years	5	5.6%
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Type of work	Midwife	23	25.6%
	Dentist	4	4.4%
	General practitioners	23	25.6%
	Nutritionist	3	3.3%
	Nurse	23	25.6%
	Dental Nurse	3	3.3%
	Counter Officer	7	7.8%
	Health Laboratory Administrator	4	4.4%
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Years of service	≤1 Year	12	13.3%
	2–5 Years	15	16.7%
	6–10 Years	27	30.0%
	11–15 Years	24	26.7%
	>15 Years	12	13.3%
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Total		90	100%

Based on the results of a study of 90 healthcare workers, the majority of respondents were female (70 respondents) (77.8%), while 20 respondents (22.2%) were male. Based on age, the majority of respondents were in the 31–40 age range, namely 45 respondents (50.0%). Based on the type of work, respondents consisted of 23 midwives (25.6%), 23 general practitioners (25.6%), 23 nurses (25.6%), 4 dentists (4.4%), 4 health laboratory technicians (4.4%), 3 nutritionists (3.3%), 3 dental nurses (3.3%), and 7 registration counter officers (7.8%). Based on length of service, the majority of respondents had a service period of 6–10 years, namely 27 people (30.0%), followed by a service period of 11–15 years, namely 24 people (26.7%), a service period of 2–5 years, namely 15 people (16.7%), and a service period of ≤1 year and >15 years, namely 12 people (13.3%) each.

T-TEST

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients (B)	t count	Sig.	Information
Constant	-18,393	-2.112	0.038	-
Motivation (X1)	1,874	4,853	< 0.001	Significant
Income Level (X2)	1,560	3,990	< 0.001	Significant
Work Environment (X3)	0.286	0.718	0.475	Not Significant
Opportunity to Achieve (X4)	1,126	2,885	0.005	Significant
Management (X5)	2,153	5,608	< 0.001	Significant
Nutritional Status (X6)	0.261	0.666	0.507	Not Significant

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Motivation

Work motivation is a crucial factor influencing healthcare worker productivity. Highly motivated healthcare workers tend to provide faster, more responsive, and more professional service to patients. The significance value is <0.001 (less than 0.05). This means that motivation has a positive and significant effect on health services. The higher the motivation of health workers, the more significantly the quality of service will improve.

Income Level

An adequate level of income can increase the job satisfaction of health workers, thereby encouraging improved performance in providing health services. Has a significance value of <0.001 . This indicates that the income received by health workers plays an important role in improving the quality of services at the Setiabudi Community Health Center.

Work environment

A comfortable and conducive work environment will increase the effectiveness of health workers and support the creation of quality health services. Having a significance value of 0.475 (greater than 0.05). Statistically, the work environment in this study did not have a significant partial effect on service improvement.

Opportunity to Achieve

Opportunities to develop careers and receive awards for work achievements can increase the work enthusiasm of health workers. It has a significance value of 0.005 (less than 0.05). This means that providing opportunities for employees to excel has a real positive impact on service.

Management

Good management in health service organizations is very important in managing resources, coordinating service activities, and improving the performance of health workers. It has a significance value of <0.001 and the highest t-value (5.608). This indicates that the Management variable is the most dominant factor influencing the improvement of health services.

Nutritional status

The physical health of healthcare workers also impacts work productivity. Healthcare workers in good physical condition are better able to perform their duties optimally. It has a significance value of 0.507 (greater than 0.05). Similar to the work environment, nutritional status does not have a significant partial effect on service quality in this research model.

COEFFICIENT OF DETERMINATION

This table is used to see how much contribution or influence all independent variables have together on the dependent variable.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	0.683	0.466	0.427	2,987

The R Square value of 0.466 indicates that the Productivity variables (Motivation, Income, Work Environment, Opportunity to Achieve, Management, and Nutritional Status) collectively contributed 46.6% to the improvement of Health Services at the Setiabudi Community Health Center. The remaining 53.4% was influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

F TEST (SIMULTANEOUS)

This table is used to determine whether all independent variables together have a significant influence on the dependent variable.

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	645,431	6	107,572	12,053	< 0.001
Residual	740,736	83	8,925		
Total	1386,167	89			

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F Calculation (12.053) > F Table: The calculated F value of 12.053 with a significance of <0.05 indicates that all independent variables simultaneously have a significant effect on health services. Significance (<0.001): Because the significance value is much smaller than 0.05, it can be concluded that H1 is accepted. Simultaneously (together), the variables of Motivation, Income Level, Work Environment, Opportunity to Achieve, Management, and Nutritional Status have a significant influence on improving Health Services at the Setiabudi Community Health Center, South Jakarta.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study reinforce the findings of Putri & Santoso (2021), who stated that internal management and coordination are key factors in the effectiveness of services at FKTP (First Level Health Facilities). Furthermore, the significance of motivation variables in increasing patient satisfaction aligns with the study by Sari et al. (2023), which emphasized that the psychological well-being of healthcare workers is directly proportional to the friendliness of the services received by the community.

Analysis of the Simultaneous Contribution of Productivity to Health Services

Based on the test results in the Model Summary appendix, the coefficient of determination (R^2) obtained was 0.466. This indicates that simultaneously, the variables of motivation, income level, work environment, opportunity for achievement, management, and nutritional status contributed 46.6% to improving health services at the Setiabudi Community Health Center. This finding is supported by research by Handayani & Wijaya (2022), which stated that the productivity of health workers in public facilities is strongly influenced by a combination of internal and managerial factors. The remaining 53.4% influence is influenced by other variables outside this research model, such as infrastructure or macro health policies.

Management as the Main Determinant Factor (X5)

The Coefficients appendix data shows that the Management variable has the highest t-value, 5.608, with a significance level of <0.001. With a Beta coefficient of 0.455, management is the most dominant variable influencing health services. This demonstrates that coordination, leadership, and supervision at the Setiabudi Community Health Center are highly effective. These findings align with a study by Putri & Santoso (2021), which emphasized that in urban community health centers, sound management is far more crucial in determining service quality than physical environmental factors alone.

Motivation (X1) and Well-being (X2) in Service

The Motivation ($t = 4.853$) and Income Level ($t = 3.990$) variables were both significant at the <0.001 level. This indicates that psychological support and financial well-being are fundamental aspects for healthcare workers. According to a study by Sari et al. (2023), guaranteed well-being minimizes work distractions, enabling healthcare workers to provide more empathetic and focused services. High motivation ensures that the responsiveness dimension in service is maintained even under high workload conditions.

Existence of Opportunities to Achieve (X4)

The Opportunity to Achieve variable has a t-value of 2.885 with a significance level of 0.005 (<0.05). This means that providing career development opportunities and work recognition has a significant impact. According to Wulandari (2024), healthcare workers who are given the space to achieve will feel a greater sense of moral responsibility towards the institution, which then translates into better service quality. Analysis of Insignificant Variables: Work Environment (X3) and Nutritional Status (X6) The appendix results show that the Work Environment (Sig. 0.475) and Nutritional Status (Sig. 0.507) have no partial effect. This is interesting because it differs from classical theory. However, when associated with the profile of respondents, the majority of whom have worked for 5-10 years, this indicates a high level of adaptation (resilience). Health workers at the Setiabudi Community Health Center are still able to provide optimal services without being directly affected by physical environmental conditions or personal nutritional status. This finding indicates that work professionalism can mitigate the limitations of physical supporting factors, a phenomenon also found in the study by Pratiwi & Setiawan (2020).

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that health worker productivity has a significant influence on improving health services at the Setiabudi Community Health Center, South Jakarta. Of the six variables studied, four (Motivation, Income, Opportunity for Achievement, and Management) proved significant, while the other two variables (Work Environment and Nutritional Status) did not show a significant influence individually on improving health services at the study site. Motivational factors, income level, work environment, opportunities for achievement, management, and nutritional status are factors that influence the productivity of health workers. Therefore, increasing the productivity of health workers needs to be a concern in the management of health facilities so that the quality of health services to the community can continue to be improved.

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